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A STUDY OF MOTIVATION: SELF DRIVEN EMPLOYEES

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Abstract:

Most employers today would like to have their employee's motivated and ready to work, but do not understand what truly motivates a person. Companies could be more efficient if the employees had an invested interest in the future of the company. There are essential needs to be met for a person, specifically an employee, to succeed in the workplace. I will examine different theories of motivations, how they are relevant to the workplace, and how employers can implement the theories to ensure happy and motivated employees.

The most important theories include: Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Herzberg's two-factor theory, Aristotle's seven causes, and the different types of motivation. Each theory is related in the fact that there are needs for all people to meet. Every employee is at a different stage in their lives, which requires different management techniques. It is shown that motivation must come from within the employee. The theories investigated will help describe how managers can influence their employees to self motivate and produce the best work possible.

There are two specific types of motivation: financial and non-financial. I will focus on ways the employers can motivate their employees using financial means as well as non-financial recognitions. In this day in time, there is not always a plentiful amount of money to spend on motivation, so it is important to understand how managers can make their employees feel important without breaking the bank. Both types need to be executed in a strategic way to provide the best results.

Lastly, I will focus on how managers are able to implement these types of motivation into their specific work place. This will show how motivation is important to all industries, and how it can change and impact the amount sales a company performs. Motivated employees will in turn create a successful company.

The paper is descriptive in nature. Author in this paper have reviewed the literature on employee motivation which is a key to effective and efficient workforce.

Keywords: Motivation, motivated employees, financial and non-financial motivation

INTRODUCTION

One may ask why there is a need for managers to spend time on motivating their employees, but the answer is to extend their existence. Employees make up an organization and if they do not have organizational commitment, then there is no incentive to excel at their jobs. A 1988 study showed that eighty-six percent of organizations struggled with attracting new employees and fifty-eight percent of those organizations expressed challenges with regards to retaining current employees (Ramlall, 52). Although this study is older, the information is still relevant today. Studies show that when ten professional employees of an organization leave, that organization loses roughly one million dollars (Ramlall, 52). In addition to the financial loss, they also suffer the loss of knowledge and

experience the individual(s) may have, which is one of the most valued employee assets. This cost could be avoided or lessened by motivating employees by keeping them involved and committed to the organization.

Two important reasons that employees should be motivated are to achieve their own personal goals and the organizational goals (Shanks, 23). In a study done by the Society for Human Resource Management, they found that eighty-six percent of the people they surveyed were satisfied with their jobs (SHRM). This number could increase if the soon to be discussed techniques are implemented in the specific work sites. In a different study by Career Vision, they found that thirty-three percent of employees feel as though they have reached a dead end in their career ("Job Satisfaction Statistics"). The research presented will discuss the research and theories of motivation, then prove there is a need for motivation in all workplaces and explain the most effective ways of motivating employees with financial and non-financial means. The final question is: how and in what ways can managers motivate their employees to make them more productive to the organization?

Research Methods:

Secondary data sources like books, journals, magazines and research data bases have been used to review the existing literature on the topic of the study.

Definition of Motivation:

The definition of motivation starts with the root word, motive. Webster's Dictionary defines motive as, something that causes a person to act. Therefore, motivation can be defined as, the act of providing motive that causes someone to act (Shanks, 24). In other words, according to Nancy Shanks, motivation causes someone to act and someone else cannot make someone motivated. It is the discretion of the person to decide if they are going to be motivated or not. Motivated and unmotivated are not opposites, but instead, there are determining factors that could cause someone to be unmotivated, such as life events and attitudes towards a specific job.

With relation to the workplace, Ray Williams, who writes for Psychology Today, defines motivation as, "With relation to the workplace, Ray Williams, who writes for Psychology Today, defines motivation as, "predisposition to behave in a purposeful manner to achieve specific, unmet needs and the will to achieve, and the inner force that drives individuals to accomplish personal organizational goals" (Williams). A person becomes motivated in order to achieve their own personal goals as well as the organizational goals. The more motivated an employee is, the more likely they are to have organizational commitment and identify themselves with the organization.

Theories of Motivation

There are many different theories that try and help explain motivation. Scientists have been studying the topic of motivation for over a century and have made tremendous progress for explaining motivation which can be interpreted into the workplace. The following are some theories that have been proven and accepted by society. These include Maslow's hierarchy of needs, Herzberg's two-factor theory, different types of motivation, such as intrinsic and extrinsic, and the PERMA model.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs:

Maslow believed every person had needs that need to be met. He transferred his idea into a triangle design. The follow displays Maslow’s hierarchy of needs (Hodder Education):

Maslow believed that people are motivated to fulfill their own needs (“Motivation Theories”). Every person starts at the bottom of the pyramid and works to achieve the goals of the next layer working to the top sector. One is not able to move on to the next level of the pyramid until the needs of the first level are met. Once they move to the next level, those needs must be met and if they are not, then it is possible to fall back down the pyramid. According to the article, “Motivation Theories”, the following is a definition of the different levels.

The first level is the physiological needs. These are the basic needs that are to be met in order to survive, including food, water, clothing, sleep, and shelter. The next step is security, which means that the person’s surroundings are not threatening to them or their family. If the environment seems to be safe, then it means that there is a sense of predictability or stability in the surroundings. Security could also include financial security so that there is no financial uncertainty in the future. This could be achieved by creating a retirement package, securing job position, and insurance. The third level is affiliation which is the need to feel a sense of belonging or to be loved. In the workplace, this means to feel as though they are a part of the group and included in the work. People have the urge to be accepted by others, especially the people they are around the most. The fourth level is explained as esteem. This is the view that one has of themselves. In order to fully understand this level, the person must have a high image of them self and encompass self respect. This level has two components: feelings of self worth, and the need for respect from others. The last and final stage of the hierarchy of needs is self actualization. This level is defined as someone being all they can be and they have met each of the previous stages. In this particular level, the person’s talents are being completely utilized. Maslow believes that no one is ever completely self actualized. People are always striving to be better and use their talents in new ways. This is important to motivation because a person must be motivated to fulfill their needs and strive for the next level until they reach self actualization. These needs motivate humans to care for themselves and live a rich life (Baltoni, 16).

Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory

One of Herzberg’s many theories is known as the Two-Factor Theory or the Motivation-Hygiene Theory. This theory is commonly related to Maslow’s theory of hierarchy of needs and was conducted in the late 1950’s. In his first steps of studying the redesigning of jobs, he looked at all the available information at the time. From this data, he decided to conduct his own study which involved two-hundred accountants and engineers. From his study he

found that the subjects he surveyed described satisfying events at work in terms of factors that were connected to the job itself (Ramlall, 57). He believed that the mental health of an employee is directly related to performing meaningful work ("Motivation Theories").

Based on the study, he discovered factors that he labeled as motivators, or job content factors, and hygiene factors, or job context. Motivators or job content factors were those that focused on work. These included achievement, work itself, advancement, recognition, responsibility, and growth ("Motivation Theories", Shanks, 27). Likewise, hygiene factors or job context are defined as factors that are related to job dissatisfaction. Examples of hygiene factors include the company, organizational policies, administration, salary, status, job security, working conditions, personal life, and interpersonal relations (Doyle, "Motivation Theories"). The organization may have control over many of these factors, but some of them they do not, such as personal life or interpersonal relationships.

Herzberg found that the factors that lead to job satisfaction are different and separate to those that may lead to job dissatisfaction (Ramlall, 57). He found that the growth needs, or the highest level of needs, are the only real motivators of employees. Employees are motivated by the existence of the motivating factors, but are only dissatisfied, not unmotivated, by the hygiene factors ("Motivation Theories"). One of Herzberg's leading arguments was, "for an employee to be truly motivated, the employee's job has to be fully enriched where the employee has the opportunity for achievement and recognition, stimulation, responsibility, and advancement" (Ramlall, 57). Herzberg found that for the employee to be motivated, they must feel personally responsible for the products produced from the job. This will have them working harder to achieve their own personal goals, as well as the goals of the organization. The employee also needs to feel like the working that they are doing is meaningful and enriching (Ramlall, 57). In order to do this and to address the different types of factors, a manager might want to consider the following ("Motivation Theories"):

- Remove some job controls
- Increase worker accountability for their own work
- Give workers complete units of work to produce
- Give greater job freedom or additional authority to workers
- Make periodic reports directly to the workers (not through the supervisor)
- Introduce new and more difficult tasks
- Assign specialized tasks to workers so they can become experts

The Four Motivations

There are four commonly defined motivations which include: extrinsic motivation, intrinsic motivation, introjected motivation, and identified motivation. Before the definitions are explained, the following charts, from Changing Minds, which is a website that collects data on psychological findings, help illustrate the importance and definitions of the four motivators ("Extrinsic Motivation", "Four Motivations.").

Definition off Different Types of Motivation	Behavior sustained by	Example
External Motivation	Environmental reward or punishment contingencies	Do work because paid to do it
Introjected Motivation	Desire to avoid internally imposed guilt & recrimination	Do work to earn money to sustain family
Identified Motivation	Desire to express important self-identifications	Do work because it is what I want to do.

External vs. Internal Motivation

Action		Non-Action	
External	Extrinsic	Identified	
Internal	Intrinsic	Introjected	

Intrinsic motivation is done for reasons that are internal to one’s self. It is for self-satisfaction and not for the fear of a consequence. The reward is within the action itself and does not need external factors to steer behavior. Extrinsic motivation comes from external factors and the actions are done because of what has been said. This means that if we are told to do something, we do it because of extrinsic motivation. Introjected motivation also comes from within one’s self, but if the action is not done, then the person is filled with guilt. The main difference between introjected and intrinsic motivation is the feeling of guilt. Lastly, identified motivation is defined as when person knows that a task needs to be completed, but does nothing to complete it ("Four Motivations"). These different definitions help define the different types of motivation that employees encounter. As extrinsic motivation rises, intrinsic motivation decreases because the person starts to only look for external rewards instead of working on something for personal satisfaction. There should always be a combination of both, but in essence, the person must be able to motivate from within to truly gain worth or a feeling of self-accomplishment from a task or goal.

These four motivators were studied by Lepper, Greene, and Nisbett in 1963. They wanted to see if extrinsic rewards had any effect on people. There are intrinsic rewards and extrinsic rewards as well. Intrinsic rewards are those that come from within a person. The reward is not tangible and is important to the individual, such as pride. There are also extrinsic rewards which are those that are given out by another person. These rewards are tangible and the individual must prove themselves to someone in order to obtain the reward, such as a bonus (Shanks, 24). Lepper, Greene, and Nisbett had two groups of children coloring and drawing. One of the groups was told that they would receive a medal for their drawings at the end and the other group was not told they would get anything. It was found that the group that was promised nothing worked harder than the group that was promised the metal (Greene and Lepper).

Intrinsic motivation was first studied through animal behavior, and then transferred into studies of human behavior (Ryan and Edward, 56). A person gains understanding of skills through acting on a previous interest. It is also important to point out that not every person is intrinsically motivated for every single task and does need some extrinsic motivation as well (Ryan and Edward, 56). Intrinsically motivated behaviors in turn feed the psychological needs of a person, such as competency or self-worth. On the other hand, extrinsic motivation has a separate reward other than feelings from within. A great example of this for people in school is that students work hard throughout the year to earn the grades they receive. The grades are the external reward that the students are motivated by. Richard Ryan and Edward Deci, the writers of “Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivations; Classic Definitions and New

Directions” state that, “because extrinsically motivated behaviors are not inherently interesting and thus must initially be externally prompted, the primary reason people are likely to be willing to do the behaviors is that they are valued by significant others to whom they feel connected, whether that be a family, a peer group or society” (Ryan and Edward, 64).

Along with motivated people, there are amotivated people. This means that “a person’s behavior lacks intentionality and a sense of personal causation” (Ryan and Edward, 61). This can be caused by many different reasons such as the person not valuing the task being done, the person not feeling as though they are adequately trained or knowledgeable to complete the task, or the person not thinking that there is a desirable outcome from the task (Ryan and Edward, 62).

PERMA Model

Dr. Martin Seligman is a well-known psychologist and has written many books on different topics regarding psychology. He is currently a professor at the University of Pennsylvania teaching psychology (University of Pennsylvania). In 2011 he published a book called *Flourish* in which he described his PERMA model. PERMA stands for positive emotion, engagement, positive relationships, meaning and accomplishment/achievement (“PERMA Model.”). Dr. Seligman says that these five categories are essential for humans to have long-lasting well-being (“PERMA Model.”).

The following definitions of the five categories are from Mind Tools and Changing Minds articles. In order for us to experience well-being, we need to have many different positive feelings throughout the day. Dr. Barbara Fredrickson, a well-known researcher in emotions, states that for every one negative feeling we have, we need to have three positive feelings to continue the current state of happiness (“PERMA”). Positive emotions include: peace, hope, love, etc. Dr. Seligman believes that people need to take the time out to identify people, places, or events that give the person pleasure so that they can focus on those and make sure to incorporate them into daily life. Secondly, we should be engaged in the work or tasks that we take part in. The engagement in work creates what is called “flow” which is when we find ourselves enjoying moment and concentrating on what we are working on. In order to increase engagement at work or in life is to decrease the amount of distractions and interruptions. The opposite of engagement is distraction. This will keep the person alert and motivated by being on task (“PERMA Model.”). Next, we need to create relationships with the people around us. It is proven that people who have meaningful relationships with those around them are happier than those people who do not. Most people will spend a majority of their life at work, so these positive relationships should start in the work setting to create a better environment.

As human beings, we need to do activities that give life meaning and enjoyment to help with lasting well-being. To do this, we should engage in activities in which make a difference bigger than we can imagine. Meaning can come internally or externally. Lastly, we need to have achievements and accomplishments in our lives. There are countless accomplishments that can be done to better ones self. All five of these categories add up to the long lasting well-being of a person. With all five, a person will be more motivated and have a better work attitude. A person must be aware of themselves and what objects or people make each of these categories richer.

Example of Motivation

When motivating employees, there are two main ways: financial motivation and non-financial motivation. A McKinsey Quarterly study found that seventy percent of organizations.

say that they use or plan on using a motivation program (Dewhurst, Guthridge, and Mohr). Many managers still believe that money is everything. Through research, it is shown that for most people non-financial rewards or recognition serve as a better motivator than money. Rewards, financial or non-financial, can be achieved

independently or as a group. There are positives and negatives to groups in the work place. Group rewards can be positive because the employees have a common bond together, the teams are more likely more productive, and communication between employees and upper management increases due to the team atmosphere. There are also some disadvantages which include: high performers are discouraged by working with low performers, there is a higher likelihood of conflict, and there can be more pressure on people when others are not completing their work (Doyle). Either individual or group rewards, the following are some examples of financial and non-financial rewards.

Financial

When speaking about financial motivators, it means that the employer spends money a lot on the reward directly, or the employee receives some kind of monetary reward. Financial rewards are short-term motivators to employees and are forgotten about later in the employee's careers. This method may not take as long for management, but it also does not have as long as a lasting effect on employees.

The most common financial reward is either a cash bonus or a salary raise. More than half the employees surveyed by the Society for Human Resources Management in 2009 said that benefits and compensation are important ("2009 Employee Job Satisfaction"). With the recent economy, compensation may be more important, but it may not serve as a strong motivator for all. A cash bonus is extra payment on top of the regular salary to encourage employees to work harder and meet company goals (Hodder Education). A bonus motivates the employee to understand exactly what the organizational goals are as well as to be a productive employee and make sure the goals are met. There are certain deadlines for bonuses which are usually around Christmas time or in the summer. Bonuses benefit the employee as well as the employer. The employee receives money that they would have not had and the employer gets the best work possible from the employee. An increase in the employee's salary is called a raise. Raises are usually done once or twice a year. These raises are based on performance, sales, and many other factors that are important to the specific organization. Raises are usually a percentage of the current salary. Raises are also associated with promotions. Promotions and raises motivate employees to be on their best behavior and perform at the top level.

Another way to motivate employees with regards to pay is commission. Pay can be based purely on commission or can be an addition to a salary. This type of pay is usually used for people in sales and is a percentage of the amount of sales that are completed. Commission pay encourages the employees to make as many sales as possible so they can increase their income (Hodder Education). The Society for Human Resources Management 2009 Employee Job Satisfaction survey says that "employees were asked how likely they were to stay with their current organization if they were offered more money, with the same benefits, at another company. Almost six out of 10 employees indicated that they would be very likely to leave their current position if they received an offer of a 30% salary increase and the same benefits package from another company" ("2009 Employee Job Satisfaction").

An employer can also offer benefits to its employees as a way of compensation and a recruitment tool to attract the most motivated employees. Benefits can range from organization to organization. There are many different packages and the employer has the option to pay for a percentage of the premiums or none at all. The less the employee has to pay, the more they are able to save and are financially motivated. In hard economic times, some employers may use benefits as a form of compensation, which keeps the pay low, but the compensation even or high ("2009 Employee Job Satisfaction"). The better the benefits package, it could make the company more appealing to candidates in the job market.

Another form of financial motivation is organizations offering employees to participate in a profit sharing program. Profit sharing, as its name implies, means that the employees get a proportion of the profit on top of their regular salary. This type of motivation is usually used in the service sector because it is hard to calculate the employees

profit contribution to the company (Hodder Education). Profit sharing is a good way to motivate employees because the more profit the company makes, the more they will receive as well. This motivates employees to work harder and be the best employee they can be. This also gives the employee a feeling that they are a part of the business since they are directly associated with it. This gives a unique common bond between all employees. A drawback of profit sharing is that there are some employees that will not work as hard as others, but they will still benefit in the profit sharing program (Hodder Education).

A last major example of financial motivation is called piece work, which means that the employee gets paid based on the amount of a product that is produced ("Financial and Non-Financial Incentives"). The employee is usually paid a minimum base and is given extra money based on how much product is produced. This method is good for employers as well as employees. The employer will have more products made at a quicker rate and the employee will be paid more on how much they produce. There are drawbacks to this type of motivation. The first problem is that this method only works if there is a way to count how much is produced by specific employees. There has to be a counting method. Secondly, employees may try to rush through the production process to make more products and the quality may decrease ("Financial and Non-Financial Incentives").

There are many ways to financially motivate employees, but these may become expected or unappreciated. There are different methods for all different sectors of the economy. Not all will work for every type of job, but there should be one that fits for an organization. If these methods are used properly, they can be extremely helpful tools to motivate employees and have them understand that their work is appreciated. Financial tools are limited due to the direct tie to the budget. Hard economic times make financial tools harder to implement. If employees are used to getting bonuses and one year they do not, they may become discouraged and decrease in productivity. It needs to be noted that managers must be careful with all types of motivation, but specifically with incentives because employees are dependent on financials for their livelihoods.

Non-Financial

Unlike financial motivators, non-financial motivators are more plentiful and can bring out the creativity of managers. This method does take more time on the manager, but it has longer lasting effects. If a manager wants to truly motivate their employee, they need to think about the individual and decide what non-financial rewards can be given to a specific employee. It needs to be said that everything requires money whether that be time, resources, materials, etc. In a McKinsey Quarterly survey, they found that the following non-financial motivators are viewed no less, or sometimes more effective than the top rated financial motivators: praise from managers, attention from leaders, and the opportunity to lead projects (Dewhurst, Guthridge, and Mohr). In this discussion of non-financial motivation, it means that there is no monetary reward given to the employee, but instead focuses on the emotional needs of the employee. There are a wide variety and many different ways to non-financially motivate employees, but this paper will only focus on a few of them. Non-financial motivators are based around the idea of recognition, which is found through many surveys to be the key driver of motivation in most employees. Dr. Gerald Graham, a professor at Wichita State University, found in one of his studies that the "top five incentives that employees mention are free. These are (1) 'a personal thank-you' from the boss, (2) a 'written thank-you' from the same, and (3) 'public praise'" (Baldoni, 149). Recognition is only effective if it is delivered in the correct way and has meaning behind it. The rewards must be meaningful and be given for an action that the manager wants repeated by other employees. To make a reward meaningful, it should be specific to the person receiving it, and it should have thought put into it. It will mean more to a person if they know the reward is sentimental and meant for them. Employees should not be given a reward for a good effort, but instead on a stellar job on a project or action. It is also important to recognize the employees that are behind the scenes and doing the background work. Without these people, the organization would not stay afloat.

There are many different ways to conduct effective recognition. The most basic way is to give a verbal compliment to the employee. This could be an acknowledgement of job well done, a good sale, or a particular action that the employee did that benefitted the organization. The compliment could be done in public or in private. This gives the employee reassurance that they are doing what their managers are looking for and that they are paying attention to the work being done. Secondly, the manager could send the employee an E-mail that explains the appreciation of the employee. This is an immediate way to show gratitude, but an E-mail is less meaningful to an employee as a hand written note. A hand written note shows the employee that the manager took the time to write a message to them. This could be hung in their work space as a “trophy” to other employees (Doyle).

A manager can also publically acknowledge an employee in front of their peers at a meeting, presentation, in the office, etc. (Doyle). There are a variety of different ways to strategize on how to go about the acknowledgement. The process can be short and sweet, or drawn out into a large ceremony for the person. Acknowledging the person in front of their peers will motivate them and have others look at them as a role model in the work place. In Shawn Doyle’s, “The Manager’s Pocket Guide to Motivating Employees” suggests that there should be a “hero” in the work place. This is someone that is looked up to and people can go to with questions. This “hero” can be made by public recognitions. Although a hero could be helpful in the workplace, but a manager must be care to not make other employees resent the person.

There are different types of rewards for short and long term goals of the organization. Rewards can also be grouped into different types. The following definitions come from Shawn Doyle’s article, “The Manager’s Pocket Guide to Motivating Employees”. The first type is a MBO reward which is when there is a common goal between the employee and the manager and if the goal is reached, then the employee receives a reward based on the terms of the agreement. This can be financial or non-financial. The second is an accomplishment reward when the manager has identified an achievement and rewards are given to the employees when the actions towards the achievement are observed. A tenure award is given to employees based on a time frame of their commitment to the organization (Doyle). All of these different types of rewards can be done non-financially. The rewards do not have to involve some type of money, which is commonly believed.

Rewards can be tricky because they have to be given correctly to avoid any complications from other employees. Rewards can create resentment among the work place. This can be avoided, given the right circumstances and making all employees feel appreciated and that their work is valued (Doyle). Managers should not over recognize people, but instead only give rewards when they are deserved. Recognition can lose its value when it is done all the time and is no longer personal to the employee. If it is overdone, employees can start to expect rewards and when they are not given when they believe they should, it can create the opposite affect and discourage the employees. Rewards should be done spontaneously so that they are a surprise and valued. The manager should also give recognition and rewards honestly (Doyle). If they see that there is a problem, then it should be addressed. If a manger follows the proper steps in giving rewards and recognition, it can be a wonderful non-financial tool to motivate employees.

One way to provide non-financial motivation is to provide an opportunity for job rotation. Job rotations allow for the employee to explore other jobs within the organization. This is a great training tool so that the employee can have a better understanding of all that jobs that are done in the organization. This also prevents the employee from getting bored in their own job and gives them the opportunity to do something different for a while (Hodder Education). This technique does not work for all areas, but is specifically good for the factory sector. Job sharing is another way to allow flexibility in the workplace and keep employees happy. Job sharing means that a job that would typically be done by one person is split up into two people who each do half the time to add up to a full time employee. This gives the employees flexibility in their work schedule (Hodder Education). It is important to make sure there is good communication between the two people so that they can work together and relay any important information that the other would need to do their job.

A good way to provide motivation as well as a sense of cohesion to a group is to allow the employees to work in teams. This is great for a task that takes different people with different skill sets. It allows employees from a range of departments to work together and become a group with a mission. The team is responsible for the decisions made, so they have to work together. Being appointed to the group is a form of non-financial motivation because it can be a prestigious accomplishment to be part of working groups. This gives each employee the opportunity to demonstrate their talents to the whole organization. A 2009 study done by the Society for Human Resources Management found that “employees rated opportunities to use their skills and abilities in their work as the fourth most important aspect of their job satisfaction” (“2009 Employee Job Satisfaction”). Employees are more likely to be confident in their work when they are doing something that they enjoy and are good at. The study also states that, “nearly one-half of employees (47%) indicated that their professional abilities/skills and the importance of their job to their organization’s overall success increased their sense of job security” (“2009 Employee Job Satisfaction”). The work given in the groups should be meaningful and used once completed. Employees want to know that what they are doing is impacting the organization in a positive manner. If the work is not valued or meaningful, then the employee could become discouraged.

Security is another non-financial motivator that can be used in the workplace. This security is used in all senses. Employees want to feel that their job is secure and will be there in years to come. This allows them to freely work and have to worry about what will happen if they lose their job. It motivated the employees to work their hardest because they are sure their work is benefiting the company. Security is also used in the physical sense. Employees do not want to feel as though they are in danger while they are at work. “Fifty-four percent of employees and 52% of HR professionals indicated that feeling safe in the work environment was very important to employee job satisfaction”, in which females ranked it more important than males (“2009 Employee Job Satisfaction”). This number has doubled from 2004 with the recent threats of violence in the workplace (“2009 Employee Job Satisfaction”). Lastly, quality circles are a good way to get employees involved, and for management to hear the concerns of the employees so that they can appropriately address them. The quality circles meet on a regular basis to analyze the work and see if there are better ways to complete it (Hodder Education). The circles benefit the organization because it will help create happier employees as well as better products. Quality circles can lead to meetings with management. When employees are able to give their input to management, it makes them feel as though their opinion is valued and their work is crucial to the organization. Through these quality groups and meetings with management, the employees are able to create meaningful relationships in the workplace which can be a good motivator. With these meaningful relationships, the employees are able to feel connected to other employees as well as to the organization (Shanks, 34).

A great example of a company that motivates their employees and has gotten a lot of recognition is Southwest Airlines. Colleen Barrett, the president and COO, says, “We want people to have fun at work. We don’t want them to think that work is, you know, this professional stuffy, stereotype, you know, leave your personality at home and become this robotic Stepford wife-type deliverer of whatever it is that you do” (Baldoni, 18). Southwest’s culture is based on recognition which is done by Barrett herself. She writes personal notes to the employees and makes appearances at employee gatherings. Southwest has worked hard to create this culture. They have jobs that are specific for recognizing employees and creating culture programs (Baldoni, 19). As well as having fun, Southwest Airlines also puts an emphasis on hard work and dedication. The employees know that they are to work hard and keep the customers happy. This type of culture has helped the business grow financially. For the sixth year, Southwest Airlines was named in the top 10 Most Admired Companies by *Fortune Magazine*.

In the article, “Southwest Airlines Employee Motivation”, it explains Southwest Airlines seven elements in employee motivation (“Southwest Airlines Employee Motivation”). The first is having a strong set of values. These values come from the organization itself as well as from the employees. The values are clear and must be accepted by all. The second element is that the employees come first, which is clear in their mission statement as well.

Southwest values their employees and makes sure that their wellbeing is valued. Third is rewards and recognition. The employees know what is given by the company when a job is well done. The fourth element is the mission of the organization. Not only is the mission statement written, but it is also believed throughout the organization. Next is the hiring process. Southwest is very rigorous in an attempt to find the best possible candidate for every position. The sixth element is distributed leadership, which means that there are strong leaders throughout the entire company. Every level has leaders and every level is training employees to become leaders. The last element is performance management. This is essential to articulate the goals to all employees and keep the organization transparent. There are many companies that value motivation in employee like Southwest does. There are also many companies that could learn from the culture that Southwest has in order to benefit their own organization.

Implications for Managers

Ways to implement financial, non-financial, and other types of motivation could be used by managers to help motivate their employees and allow them to be the best that they can be. If taken seriously, managers have the opportunity to change the culture of the organization and create one where employees are valued and motivated. It needs to be noted that not every employee is motivated in the same way. Every employee is different and has different needs. The manager needs to take this into account and recognize the differences between each employee to make sure they are helping them meet their needs. People may not necessarily be motivated by one particular factor, but it could be a combination of things that really want them to work. The following recommendations could have extreme lasting effects on the organizations and the employees working for them. Aristotle says that every action that someone takes is due to one of seven causes that he identified (Aristotle). These causes include: chance, nature, compulsions, habit, reasoning, anger, or appetite ("Aristotle's Seven Causes"). Managers should take the time to understand why their employees are performing the way that they are. First, a manager should be a leader. This will give the employees something to look up to. It will also encourage the employees to perform on the same level as the manager. The manager should also display the actions that he/she wants from their employees. It is a lead by example kind of attitude that will have employees trying to behave the same. If an employee is looking to advance their career, then they can learn from their manager exactly how to act when they reach that promotion. By leading by example, managers should create an environment where their employees feel that they are able to perform up to their potential (Ramlall, 58). John Baldoni, the author of *Great Motivation Secrets of Great Leaders* says that, "leaders need followers to follow them; organizations need leaders to lead them" (Baldoni, 3). Baldoni also says that leadership can be described by two things: trust and results. The employees must be able to trust their manager, which in turn must create the results they are looking for. In order to gain trust, they must be able to lead by example and the employees must feel that they have the support and guidance from their leader. Leaders are not directly able to motivate their employees, but indirectly by creating an environment in which the employee is able to motivate themselves (Baldoni, 4).

From the Society for Human Resources Management findings of what motivates employees, they believe that employers are able to get the best talent possible if they follow what motivates employees. Being able to use personal skills was ranked highly in what creates job satisfaction. Therefore, employers should make this a priority so that their employees are able to use their skills and abilities to their fullest ("2009 Employee Job Satisfaction"). This will give the employees the opportunity to feel that they are valued, as well as being used to their fullest potential. This will motivate them to do their best since they are working in their professional area. "The first challenge is to motivate employees to work toward helping the organization achieve its goals. The second is to motivate employees to work toward achieving their own personal goals" (Shanks, 23). A manager should make sure that they are meeting these two goals for their employees.

First, an organization should make sure that they start from the beginning of the process, the hiring process. The following information is from Shawn Doyle's, *The Manager's Pocket Guide to Motivating Employees* (Doyle). Doyle says that in order to create a motivated working place, it must start with hiring motivated people. This can be

done by conducting multiple interviews to make sure that the person is exactly who the managers believe them to be. It also helps identify if the prospective employee will fit in with the rest of the organization. First, a phone interview should be done to screen the applicants and make sure only the best move on to the next round. There should next be an initial interview to get to know the person on a basic level. There should then be at least one or two more interviews to get to know that applicant better to make sure that they indeed fit in with the organizational culture. The hiring manager should be the one to make the final decision. They know what their office is like and exactly what they are looking for. Human resources should be involved to make sure that the hiring process is legal and going correctly, but the hiring manager should make the final decision on the applicant to hire. After the hiring process, the employees first few days are very important. The employee should feel welcomed because the first few days are the true impression they have on the organization.

Again, Doyle believes that the new employee should be given an accurate job description. This will motivate the employee because they will be aware of exactly what they are supposed to be doing. Also, from the manager's perspective, this is a way for them to hold the employee accountable for their work. The job description should be done in writing so that the employee has the opportunity to go back and review. Also, if it is in writing, then there is no vagueness in what is supposed to be done. Along with the job description, the employee should be told the importance of their job. This will motivate them by showing how valued they are in the work place. It will also create an organizational web and show where they fit in within the organization. Once they realize where they are in the company, they will then be able to see how their job relates to all other jobs. Lastly, the employee should be told about the organizational goals and where the manager sees the organization heading in short term and long term time. This can be done in orientation, annual reviews, communication, actions, etc. The goals should constantly be discussed so that the employees and even the manager, does not forget about them.

There are many different ways that managers can make sure that their employees are motivated. First, managers should expect the best from their employee. If they did not think that the employee could do the task, then they should not have been hired in the first place. It is motivating to employees to know that their managers believe that they can be the best, and that they expect it (Shanks, 33). People will be as good as others believe they are. Desirable behavior should be rewarded properly. Work places should be fun and pleasant. Since most of someone's life is spent at the work place, it should be a place that they enjoy going instead of dreading. Managers should focus on their employees and their needs. Every employee is at a different stage and has different needs. Ramlall and Thomas say, "Employees have multiple needs based on their individual, family, and cultural values. In addition, these needs depend on the current and desired economic, political, and social status; career aspirations; the need to balance career, family, education, community, religion, and other factors" (Ramlall, 58). When the manager takes the employees needs into consideration, they are displaying a helpful behavior. Through studies, it has been shown that those who have positive attitudes are more willing to help others (Staw, Sutton, and Pelled, 56). If the manager is willing to help their employees, then they can help with the development of that employee. Employee would rather be challenged in their work and if they have a helpful manager at their side, they can be confident (Ramlall, 58).

Lastly, every employee was hired for a reason and they all work for the same organization. Everyone should be treated equal. There should not be someone who receives every award and gets all of the attention. The authors from *Harvard Management Update* agree that employees seek equity, achievement, and camaraderie ("Why Your Employees Are Losing Motivation"). Employees want to be treated fairly in the workplace. They also want to receive the respect that they deserve. Employees also want to feel proud of their accomplishments, and they want their employer to also be proud of them. Lastly, they want to have good, lasting relationships with those they work with. A manager should try to achieve these goals. The authors believe that managers can achieve these by providing recognition. Again this can be financial recognition as well as non-financial recognition. They also say that managers can coach employees and communicate with them.

Managers and employees have the responsibility to make sure that the work place can be the best that it can be. It has been explained what the managers can do to make sure that employees are happy and motivated, but employees also have a responsibility to make sure that they accepting the motivation from within. Baldoni says that employees “need to open themselves up to the examples of communication, coaching, challenging, and recognition” (Baldoni, 209). A work place environment is more likely to succeed if all parties are willing to participate.

Conclusion

Motivation is a complex concept and can help or harm an organization depending on how it is used within an organization. If a manager takes the time to understand the needs of his/her employees, then the recognition can be extremely useful. There have been many philosophers who have tried to understand what motivates people, but every person is different and a theory cannot describe all people. It is understandable the managers have a full time job and do not have much down time to be spending on rewards, but it also gives them the opportunity to understand their employees and connect with them on a personal level.

Managers are not the only ones who can recognize others in the workplace. Employees can recognize each other as well. It has been proven to that one cannot directly motivate someone else, but they can give them the tools they need to motivate themselves. Managers are the resources for employees and they should make sure that their work environment is pleasant and desirable. This will help the productivity and improvement of their employees. If the above suggestions are implemented properly, managers will have a fully motivated team.

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Sumaiva Mukadam / A Study of Motivation: Self Driven Employees

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